

LEVELS OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF LOCAL EXECUTIVE AUTHORITIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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During the years of independence, the need to reform and improve the activities of local government, which is a lower level of the executive branch of government in the Republic of Uzbekistan, has become a topical issue. This is because the executive committees of the Soviets of People's Deputies, which were introduced in the Republic of Uzbekistan as a model of the former Soviet Union and have long been an executive and commanding body, did not meet modern requirements at all. They were under the strong influence of the party authorities and could not decide anything on their own. Apparently, the above problems could not be solved under the rule of the command-and-control system. These, in turn, put the reform of the local government system as a topical issue for the leadership of the Republic.

For a long time, local executive bodies have been entrusted with the important tasks of leading the development of the economy, cultural and educational activities, control over labor and consumption standards, providing various services to the population, protection of property, public order, protection of natural resources and the environment. and could not perform other tasks adequately. These reasons necessitated the creation of a new system of local executive bodies. Such a body became the governors.

Of particular importance was the introduction of the position of khokimiyat (institute) in Uzbekistan in order to improve the activities of executive bodies, increase their capacity, more clearly define their rights and responsibilities. In order to restructure local executive bodies, improve their system and activities, the post of Tashkent mayor was established for the first time in Uzbekistan, and he was elected on December 29, 1991 by the people of Tashkent. On January 4, 1992, the Law "On reorganization of local authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted, establishing the post of governor as a body of local executive power in all regions of the country. The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov praised the establishment of the post of hokim (governor) of the republic ,

saying: Due to their activities and the presence of social forces supporting the reforms, political and economic stability is maintained in our country”

The adoption of the new Constitution of Uzbekistan on December 8, 1992 marked a new stage in the activities of local executive authorities. For the first time in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the division of local government into representative and executive authorities has been strengthened at the constitutional level (Article 102 of the Constitution). Executive bodies - governors - will be formed in the provinces, cities and districts. In contrast to the representative bodies, governors were also formed in the districts that make up the city.

On September 2, 1993, the Law "On Local Government" was adopted. It defines the main tasks of the Councils of People's Deputies and governors on the basis of the norms of Articles 102-103 of the Constitution. Article 1, according to the third paragraph, states that "the Council of People's Deputies and the governor shall carry out tasks of socio-economic development common to the region, district and city, local laws, resolutions of the Oliy Majlis, the President and the Cabinet of Ministers documents, implementation of decisions of higher Kengashes of People's Deputies, khokims, relations between public authorities and citizens' self-government bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, involvement of the population in the management of regions, districts and cities. Local representative bodies have a two-tier system. According to Article 99 of the Constitution, "Councils of People's Deputies headed by governors in regions, districts and cities (except for cities subordinate to the district) are representative bodies of power, which decide issues within their competence in the interests of the state and citizens." Article 1 of the Law on Local Government states that "Councils of People's Deputies in regions, districts and cities (except for cities subordinate to the district) are representative bodies of state power." This was due to the need for local executive authorities. Thus, the system of khokims of the Republic of Uzbekistan - a set of khokims of regions (Tashkent city) and cities and districts was established. Article 103 of the Constitution enshrines the principle of monopoly, stating that "governors of regions, districts and cities exercise their powers on the basis of monopoly and are personally responsible for the decisions and activities of the bodies they lead." This rule not only emphasizes the importance of individual leadership in the activities of governors, but also strengthens their personal responsibility. In this case, the governor is not only personally responsible for his own activities and decisions, but also for the activities of the body he heads, which strengthens the responsibility of governors. One of the main

reasons for the appointment of the governor was to strengthen the relationship between the central and local executive bodies, the lower bodies to carry out the documents of the higher bodies without exception, to strengthen the control of the higher bodies over the activities of the lower bodies.

Subsequent reforms in the system of local government in the country began in 2003. On the basis of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan" On Amendments and Additions to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. 470-II of April 24, 2003, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan sentences were removed.

Pursuant to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-89 of April 11, 2007, the second part of Article 102 of the Constitution reads: approved by the Council of Deputies. Thus, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan can now appoint and dismiss governors of regions and the city of Tashkent without the approval of the Council of People's Deputies.

Subsequent reforms in the system of local executive power were carried out on November 12, 2010 on the basis of the report of the first President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov at the joint session of the Legislative Chamber and Senate of the Oliy Majlis of Uzbekistan. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-366 of April 16, 2014 amended the second part of Article 103 of the Constitution in the following wording: submits reports on the issues of which the relevant decisions are made by the Council of People's Deputies ". This, in turn, is a specific manifestation of the democratization of public administration. After all, the accountability of the head of the local executive power, ie the governor of the region, district or city, to the Council of People's Deputies belongs to the forms of interdependence of the branches of government and the principle of mutual restraint.

Today, the main task of state and local governments is to form an effective system of local government capable of socio-economic development and political stability of local structures that can meet the needs of modern society in global states. Optimization of the local government system means the creation of a rational model of local government in our country in today's specific socio-political and economic conditions.

In our opinion, achieving political, economic and organizational independence of local authorities should not be the main goal for the modern development of the political system of Uzbekistan. Local governments are part of the public administration system and are

integrated into a common public administration system according to their nature and functional goals. Because they operate in the territory of Uzbekistan, it may not contradict the general state principles and directions of domestic and foreign policy of the state. Second, they are specific agents of state action to implement public policy at the local level. In local governments, all spheres of public life should be developed on the basis of state policy, limited only by the scope of this local formation.

Also, people living in regions, districts, cities and under the influence of local authorities are citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan and are under state protection, which imposes certain responsibilities on local authorities and forces them to protect and comply with the rights and freedoms of citizens.

Unfortunately, scientific and political practice is aimed at solving the problem of the independence of the local government system, which in fact leads to a change in the goals of the local government system and its bodies. Instead of fulfilling their important role of developing the regions and improving the quality of life of the population, local government leaders are actively pessimistic about the dependence of local government on the state.

In our view, the recognition of this fact as a priori invincible in some areas and the efforts of governors should be aimed at achieving independence in areas where the functioning and functioning of the entire local government system is impossible. For example, the limitation of powers, financial and economic security of local authorities, the exercise of certain state powers, and so on.

The main directions of the activities of local authorities are the interaction with the population and institutions, civil society, which is the political essence of the activities of local authorities. The main principle of organizing such interaction is openness. The activities of public authorities, the system of local government should be transparent, the population should be aware of the activities of these bodies.

The principle of openness helps to democratize governance, its control by society, as well as to influence citizens to make decisions that affect their interests, rights and freedoms. Methods of ensuring transparency should be reflected in the norms of law at the local level and formed in practice.

Consistent implementation of the principle of transparency in the activities of regional, district and city bodies will allow citizens to control the activities of local authorities in addressing issues of local importance. The effectiveness of such control depends on the organization and operation of

the city information service, as well as what conditions are created for the activities of the media organization of the city organization.

The effectiveness of the activities of any organization or body is ensured when there is control. Local authorities also need to create new forms and methods of administrative control, including institutions of public control. The level of local government is closest to the population and the essence of local governance is reflected in the participation of citizens in solving local problems. The possibilities of local authorities here are limitless, because it is at this level of public power that society can directly implement forms of democracy.

Thus, an important task of local authorities is to involve citizens in their activities, which ensures the legitimacy of local government and increases the level of public confidence in it. In general, effective interaction between local government and society is facilitated by addressing the following tasks:

- the activities of local authorities should be open, transparent and understandable to the population, providing access to the process;
- it is necessary to reconsider the management of local authorities and adapt it to the specific needs of society;
- a radical restructuring of the bureaucratic system is required for the effective development of local government;
- at the local level, areas and problems that really need to be managed and addressed need to be constantly monitored;
- at the local government level, conventional methods of communication should be gradually transformed into a process of communication as close as possible to the population;
- it is necessary to introduce new methods of governance at the local level, for example, to further strengthen the system of medium-term and long-term planning at the legislative level, the "single window" system and services to the local population via the Internet;
- should be based on the initiative of the adoption of legal documents at the local level and the interests of citizens;
- it is necessary to change the culture of governance, which means accepting the initiatives and ideas of citizens as an impetus for action;
- it is necessary to develop long-distance cooperation and international long-distance networks;
- it is necessary to develop a system of regional public self-government at the local level, to reform the process of public hearings, to hold local referendums and polls more often.

30 of the State Program on the implementation of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 in the "Year of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy " sets the task "Ensuring the participation of local governments in decision-making at the national level" until April 1, 2020. According to him, the draft law envisages the development of a draft normative legal act and the procedure for coordination of draft normative legal acts on socio-economic development of regions and local programs with the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city khokimiyats. In addition, paragraph 28 of this State Program sets the task of "taking measures to increase the efficiency of local executive authorities", according to which until July 1, 2020 in the development of draft regulations and projects:

to study the issues of revising the powers of governors and the transfer of non-specific and duplicative functions to the relevant bodies;

development of clear criteria and targets for assessing the performance of governors;

development of the Territorial Development Index in order to create a system of comprehensive assessment of the activities of local executive authorities;

to study the issues of policy-making in the regions, financial support to local budgets and incentives for leaders .

One of the most serious problems for us is that the functions and powers of the state are overly centralized. For example, there are currently 64 types of licenses, of which 21 are issued by the Cabinet of Ministers and 40 by central authorities. Three of these licenses fall under the jurisdiction of regional khokimiyats and only one under the jurisdiction of district khokimiyats. All this has a negative impact on local structures in carrying out independent work to address pressing socio-economic problems in the regions. It is necessary to refrain from excessive centralization of public administration. This requires the transfer of many powers from central government to regional authorities.

Innovative technologies are one of the foundations for optimizing the activities of local authorities. Innovative technologies are not yet widespread in the local government system due to the lack of understanding of the innovative potential of regions and individual local structures, the lack of understanding of the need to introduce innovative technologies in local government practice, low professionalism of local

officials, innovative projects and innovative management methods. lack of funding, lack of government support for science and research.

Innovations in the system of local government mean innovations, the result of which is the existence of social, political and economic effects in the entire system of local government in Uzbekistan, as well as in the relations of a particular local structure, and the formation of positive public opinion. In our view, innovation in local governance can be viewed from several perspectives:

first, it is about the application of innovative methods in the implementation of economic functions in local governments. This implies, first of all, the development of the economic sphere;

secondly, the interaction with the population, the need for innovative methods in the organization of public administration at the local level in the internal management part of local authorities.

It should be noted that the innovation process will be systematic as a condition for the introduction of innovations at the local government level. Therefore, not only employees of local authorities, but also structures should be ready for its introduction, and in addition it should be supported by the local community.

In this regard, local authorities, local communities are fully informed about the plans and goals of local authorities to implement innovations, their content and essence, as well as constant interaction with the local structure, the region and the outside scientific community.

The introduction of an additional mechanism for monitoring and coordinating the effectiveness of the executive branch is an important and promising issue.

There should be regular feedback in the form of continuous training of local employees, monitoring the strengths and weaknesses of local government development, creating a channel for gathering reasonable proposals that often do not fit into narrow legal bodies, and studying the attitude of local communities to innovations.

In our opinion, due to the specificity of the political culture of the population, the high level of distrust in local government, it is necessary to introduce innovations using "soft" methods. In other words, it is about adapting innovations to the local conditions of development of all spheres of social life.

The practice of introducing innovative technologies into the activities of local authorities should be based on the principle that they meet the interests and needs of local communities, increase the level of citizen

participation in local self-government, focus on social harmony, justice, efficiency and transparency.

The effectiveness of local government can be considered to be that the results of the activities of local authorities meet the requirements and expectations of the local community as much as possible. Thus, the main criterion for assessing the performance of local authorities is not only economic growth, but also the satisfaction of the population, business and socio-political organizations with the activities of local authorities. The most important thing is that as a result of these reforms, we must create a prosperous and decent living environment for our people.

It is advisable to use the SMART method in the continuous evaluation of the results of managerial activities in local government. According to him, the goal should be specific, measurable, accepted, realistic, time-dependent.

The legal consolidation and introduction of innovations in the activities of local authorities should be based on the principle of "transparency of the decision-making process at the local level" Public discussion of decisions at the local level, ease of access to information about them, online coverage of meetings of government bodies and working meetings, the need for experts to evaluate the results of decisions, their monitoring, etc. should become necessary tools. The mandatory control system has a special role in ensuring the effectiveness of local government and local self-government. The rule that central government bodies work in coordination with local authorities in resolving issues of local importance is being put into practice.

Such a system of control must be controlled by the central, local authorities, internal control and monitoring of its activities, elements of public control are inevitable. The sphere of control should be determined in accordance with the principle of separation of powers, the independence of local government and should be primarily aimed at protecting the interests and rights of citizens.

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